
Role of Library in New Education Policy 2020

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Abstract:

The New Education Policy 2020 (NEP2020) the first education policy of the 21st century to replace the 34 years old National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986. The NEP 2020 is based on the foundational pillars Access, Affordability, Equity, Quality, and Accountability. This article discusses the importance of Libraries in teaching and learning and highlights the role of libraries for all levels of education. Now a day the Libraries support 24x7 hours access to its resources for the growth of knowledge and skills of the users. The Library resources are for use by the readers and hence are as important as food for human life.

In rapidly transforming our education system, the library resources and users have undergone drastic changes. Today's Libraries store knowledge and information in digital form for all age group people like the students, teacher, and scientist.

Keyword: NEP, College, School Library

Introduction:

Education is fundamental for achieving full human potential, developing an equitable and just society, and promoting National development. Providing universal access to quality education is the key to India's continued ascent, and leadership on the global stage in terms of economic growth, social justice and equality, scientific advancement, national integration, and cultural preservation. Universal high-quality education is the best way forward for developing and maximizing our country's rich talents and resources for the good of the individual, the society, the country, and the world.

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) was launched by Ministry of Education in India on 29 July 2020. The

new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986. The policy is providing proper guidance document for elementary education to higher education including vocational training in Indian subcontinent. The policy aims at transformation of India's education system. The nature of NEP 2020 is kind of advisory and it is up to the states, institutions, and schools to decide its implementation. The National Education Policy 2020 outlines the vision of India's new education system as under:

“National Education Policy 2020 envisions an India-centric education system that contributes directly to transforming our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society by providing high-quality education to all.”^{1, 2, 3}

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Vision of National Education Policy:

The National Education Policy 2020 has a vision of creating an India-centric education system that directly contributes to transforming our nation into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society sustainably. The policy aims to achieve this by providing high-quality education to all individuals. A primary objective of the policy is to increase state expenditure on education from around 4% to 6% of the GDP.

The role of Libraries as per New Education Policy of India will increase many folds.

“A library is more important than university because library can function without a university whereas university cannot do without library”. Dr. Shankar Dayal Sharma

The Objectives of the Study are as Follows:

1. To increase awareness about the New Education Policy 2020;
2. To highlight importance of library in education system;

3. To discuss changing landscape of learning and education;
4. To develop adequate Library resources and reading habits.

Special Features of National Education Policy 2020:

1. Universal Access at All Levels of schooling from pre-primary school to Grade 12;
2. Quality early childhood care and education for all children between 3-6 years;
3. New Curricular and Pedagogical Structure (5+3+3+4);
4. Establishing National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy;
5. Emphasis on promoting multilingualism and Indian languages; The medium of instruction until at least Grade 5, but preferably till Grade 8 and beyond, will be the home language/mother tongue/local language/regional Language.
6. Setting up of a new National Assessment Centre, PARAKH (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis Of Knowledge for Holistic Development);
7. Equitable and inclusive education - Special emphasis given on Socially and Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs);
8. Robust and transparent processes for recruitment of teachers and merit based performance;
9. Ensuring availability of all resources through school complexes and clusters;
10. Exposure of vocational education in school and higher education system;

11. Increasing GER in higher education to 50%;
12. Holistic Multidisciplinary Education with multiple entry/exit options;
13. NTA to offer Common Entrance Exam for Admission to HEIs;
14. Establishment

Provision in NEP 2020 for Libraries:

The NEP 2020 has emphasized on the importance of libraries and books by highlighting on various aspects including development of enjoyable and inspirational books in Indian languages, availability and accessibility of books in school/public libraries, strengthening of libraries and building a culture of reading across the country.

The policy also highlights that steps will be taken to ensure the accessibility of books to disable and differently-abled persons. The government, with the help of both public and private sector institutions, will devise strategies to improve the quality and attractiveness of books.

NEP Para Provisions Regarding Libraries and Books:

- Enjoyable and inspirational books for students at all levels will be developed, including through High-quality translation (technology assisted as needed) in all local and Indian languages, and will be made available extensively in both school and local public libraries.
- Public and school libraries will be significantly expanded to build a culture of reading across the Country.
- Digital libraries will also be established.
- School libraries will be set up - particularly in villages - to serve the community during non-school Hours, and book clubs may meet in public/school libraries to further facilitate and promote Widespread reading.
- A National Book Promotion Policy will be formulated, and extensive initiatives will be Undertaken to ensure the availability, accessibility, quality, and readership of books across geographies, languages, levels, and genres.
- The first requirement in this direction will be to ensure decent and pleasant service conditions at Schools. Adequate and safe infrastructure, including working toilets, clean drinking water, clean and attractive spaces, electricity, computing devices, internet, libraries, and sports and recreational resources will be provided to all schools to ensure that teachers and students, including children of all genders and children with disabilities, receive a safe, inclusive, and effective learning environment and are comfortable and inspired to teach and learn in their schools.
- Sanction of library rooms may be proposed in schools not having library rooms in the annual Work plan and budget proposal of the States/UT for consideration. The proposal may include the Cost for civil work, furniture, Almira, racks, fixing and fittings
- Alternative forms of schools, will be encouraged to preserve their traditions or alternative Pedagogical styles.

- Libraries and laboratories will be strengthened and adequate reading materials like books, Journals, etc., and other teaching-learning materials will be made available.
- A key initiative in this direction will be to use schools/ school complexes after school hours and On weekends and public library spaces for adult education courses which will be ICT equipped when possible and for other community engagement and enrichment activities.
- Improving the availability and accessibility of books is essential to inculcating the habit of reading within our communities and educational institutions.
- This Policy recommends that all communities and educational institutions - schools, colleges, Universities and public libraries - will be strengthened and modernized to ensure an adequate Supply of books that cater to the needs and interests of all students, including persons with Disabilities and other differently-abled persons.
- The Central and State governments will take steps to ensure that books are made accessible and Affordable to all across the country including socio-economically disadvantaged areas as well as those living in rural and remote areas.
- Both public and private sector agencies/institutions will devise strategies to improve the quality and attractiveness of books published in all Indian languages.
- Steps will be taken to enhance online accessibility of library books and further broad basing of digital libraries.
- Other steps will include:
 - Strengthening all existing libraries,
 - setting up rural libraries and reading rooms in disadvantaged regions, making widely available reading material in Indian languages, opening children's libraries and mobile libraries, o establishing social book clubs across India and across subjects, and fostering greater collaborations between education institutions and libraries.

Conclusion:

This article discusses the importance of Libraries in teaching and learning and highlights the role of libraries for all levels of education. Now a day the Libraries support 24x7 hours access to its resources for the growth of knowledge and skills of the users. The Library resources are for use by the readers and hence are as important as food for human life.

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